

Artificial Fairy Tales: An Experiment in Computational Narratology

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1. Background

The transformative potential of generative artificial intelligence has been increasingly exploited by scholars of computational literary studies (CLS). Specifically, large language models (LLMs) have been utilised not only for annotation tasks ([10]: 211) but also for investigating complex narrative phenomena [15][16], while theoretical remarks regarding their application have also been articulated [14]. LLMs themselves, however, represent a valuable research object for CLS: since they effectively serve as “compression algorithms for human culture” [2], investigating their inner composition and workings can offer valuable insights into cultural expression, including literature, despite known biases in their training data. Following the example of previous studies on LLM-generated dramas [8] and short stories [9], this paper aims at further exploring the storytelling abilities of generative AI by investigating how these models are able to creatively reconstruct human-written narratives from a given premise.

2. Experiment setup

Among pre-LLMs approaches to automatic story generation [1], many studies, like [7], operationalise the theoretical framework built by Vladimir Propp in his seminal work on the Russian fairy tales collected by Alexander Afanasyev [13]. In this experiment, we use as reference a similar compilation, the Brothers Grimm’s *Children and Household Tales* (1812-57), and work with Google’s state-of-art *Gemini* LLM [6] due to its convenient API access policy.¹

Our pipeline begins by scraping Wikipedia to collect the titles of 168 Grimm fairy tales² and their (arguably) human-written summaries. In an attempt at *data archeology* [4], we ask the LLM to summarise each story, in order to assess to which extent the content is already memorised in

¹ See https://ai.google.dev/tutorials/python_quickstart.

² I.e. those indexed in the corresponding category:
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Grimms' Fairy Tales](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Grimms'_Fairy_Tales).

its training set. We then prompt Gemini to construct a simple narrative based on ‘key components’ we identified as peculiar for each story.

To this aim, we prototyped a lightweight operationalisation of the concept of “story”, loosely based on Proppian narratology and tentatively relying on just three elements: *character(s)* (marked according to the Proppian taxonomy of *dramatis personae* ³), *setting(s)*, and *issue(s)* (i.e. Propp’s *motivation* ⁴). Table 1 shows a sample prompt, asking for a retelling of the *Hare’s Bride* tale.

At this stage, we decided to single out these components manually for better accuracy, even if computational options were available. We also operated in a zero-shot setting and generated only the bare narrative structure (i.e. the *fabula*) to ease later qualitative comparison; results were stored in a dataframe (Table 2).

Write a short fairy tale using these elements. Please provide only the fabula or sequence of events.

- TITLE: “The Hare's Bride”
- CHARACTER(S): a little girl (*hero*), a speaking hare (*antagonist*)
- SETTING(S): little house with a garden of cabbages, the hare's hut
- ISSUE(S): the hare eats the little girls' mother's cabbages, the hare wants to marry the girl

Table 1. Example of prompt used.

Title	Index No.	Human-written summary (Wikipedia)	AI-written summary (Gemini)	AI-written retelling (Gemini)
<i>The Hare’s Bride</i>	66	Once there was a woman and her daughter who lived together in a pretty little house and whose pretty little garden had a plot full of cabbages [...]	A cunning hare hatches a plan to deceive a young woman into marriage. He cleverly transforms himself into a handsome gentleman [...]	A little girl helps her mother tend to their precious cabbage garden. One day, they discover a mischievous hare munching on their cabbages [...]

³ Conventionally, the seven main functions identified by Propp are given as follows: *hero* (*protagonist*), *antagonist*, *donor*, *helper*, *sought-for person*, *anti-hero*, *dispatcher* ([13]: 79-80 and ff).

⁴ “By motivations are meant both the reasons and the aims of personages which cause them to commit various acts. Motivations often add to a tale a completely distinctive, vivid coloring, but nevertheless motivations belong to the most inconstant and unstable elements of the tale. In addition, they represent an element less precise and definite than functions or connectives” ([13]: 75).

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Table 2. Output dataframe.

3. Perspectives

Currently, our focus remains on completing the corpus collection. In the next phase, we do not plan to perform a fully-fledged evaluation of the results using automatic and machine-learned methods or multiple human annotators ([1][5][3]). Instead, we strive to gain insights into the implicit ‘storytelling strategy’ of the model through a qualitative synoptic review of its outputs (summaries and retellings). This approach will enable us to develop a typology of the ‘creative departures’ made by the AI, highlighting recurring patterns in its rewriting of well-known texts (e.g. through bowdlerisation of ‘problematic’ plot twists) and thus starting to delineate a morphology of artificially generated fairy tales.

4. References

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